

Hard-pressed, but not crushed: A disposition of the heart in the space in-between

Rebecca Kan and Eliza Yeo Hui

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Provocation

As we locate ourselves in the space between professional identities, we feature ourselves as third space practitioners who are caught in the space in-between as academic developers in a higher arts education. The promises of this space arise when we probe deeper: artists have a disposition to creatively creolise boundaries between the centre and the periphery, “dividing the familiar and the foreign, the owned and the borrowed, the near and the far” (Sztabińska, 2014, p. 45). At the same time, school administrators behold dispositions to “establish a safe school environment, creating a trusting school culture, and setting high student academic expectations” (Pregot, 2016, p. 42).

With such a combustion of strengths, this dialogic exchange seeks to understand how dispositions emerge through the in-between. We question how we may develop the professional identity of third space practitioners, in order to be renewed day by day. As Routledge (1996, p. 406) surmises, this is “a place of invention and transformational encounters, a dynamic in-between space that is imbued with the traces, relays, ambivalences, ambiguities and contradictions, with the feelings and practices of both sites, to fashion something different, unexpected.”

This article explores the first-hand accounts of how two female colleagues, Rebecca Kan and Eliza Yeo (hereafter RK and EY) exchanged views about experiences in the space in-between.

About us

RK: I am a musician and musicologist by training, and educationalist by profession. Having breathed in performance and Baroque music research for the first twenty-six years of my life, I settled back in Singapore as a lecturer at a pioneering arts academy in Singapore. In 2010, I was appointed as Vice-Dean of Teaching and Learning to jumpstart academic policies and quality assurance processes at the academy. Socialised in the calling to spearhead pedagogy, research and partnerships to enhance the quality of higher arts education, I decided to embark on my second doctorate in professional education just before COVID-19 struck. In February 2023, I was conferred an EdD for my research on the in-between space of learning. It was at the beginning of the same year that there was a major re-organisation, where I was offered two appointments at the Teaching and Learning Centre (as Associate Dean of Curriculum and Pedagogy) and Faculty of Performing Arts (as Associate Dean of Degree Studies).

EY: I majored in social sciences in university, and thereafter, found myself in the HR space in a tertiary arts institution. I began my career in talent acquisition of administrative staff and

eventually transitioned to recruiting for the faculty and schools two years ago. I also hold the portfolio of Learning & Development; where exciting collaborations and partnership with the academic side comes in, together with strategic planning to upskill and move our unique position to a university college. Prior to the learning function, I helmed Employee Engagement, which allowed me to build rapport with my colleagues in an informal and light-hearted environment. From 30 July 2024, HR was re-named as People Excellence Office to develop and execute a comprehensive People Strategy in support of our academy's goals.

With such a combustion of profiles, both of us chose to use collaborative auto-ethnography to examine our own agency and identity in the space in-between. Collaborative auto-ethnography is a methodology that facilitates two or more individuals engage in dialogue to compare and contrast their lived experiences on a common phenomenon together (Norris et al., 2012). We conducted exchange in the month of October 2024, where we had five email exchanges and two 30-minute calls on Teams to exchange our views.

Our inquiry

In *L'évolution Créatrice*, the French philosopher Henri Bergson argued for in-betweens that focused on open and creative futures – between reason and intuition, between order and chaos, between predictability and unpredictability, between inclusion and exclusion, between rationality and creativity. Bergson (1907) described the indeterminacy and uncertainty of the in-between as “the space of becoming”: not just about movement towards a “preformed version of the real”, but a potential that threatens the identities that frame it. The in-between—as a space that celebrates an otherness to unfold in an autonomous and unpredictable fashion, as opposed to what is actual in body and material—forms the inspiration for kindling futures (Kan, 2023). As Routledge (1996, p. 406) surmises, this is “a place of invention and transformational encounters, a dynamic in-between space that is imbued with the traces, relays, ambivalences, ambiguities and contradictions, with the feelings and practices of both sites, to fashion something different, unexpected.”

“**Traces**” refer to influences and encounters of the past that continue to shape the present.

“**Relays**” are the processes of transmission to navigate between different individuals, faculties, or organisational structures. “**Ambivalences**” refer to the tensions that arise between institutional goals and personal agency, or balancing multiple, sometimes opposing, roles. “**Ambiguities**” represent the uncertainty, lack of clarity, or fluidity inherent in a space that defies traditional boundaries. “**Contradictions**” refer to the inherent conflicts that arise when working in a space that must reconcile opposing principles or practices that “fashion something different, unexpected” (Routledge, 1996, p. 406). In our exchange, we capture dispositions of the heart that emerge, as we navigate between polarities to seek new perspectives and critical insights as third space practitioners.

Against this backdrop, we invite you to reflect on these questions:

1. How do you perceive the “traces” of past experiences or institutional cultures shaping the current in-between space of your professional roles?
2. How do the “relays” of communication and decision-making function in this in-between space? Do they create opportunities for bridging gaps, or do they reinforce separations?
3. How do you navigate “ambivalence” inherent in your role, where you must balance institutional priorities with institutional/personal core values?

4. How do you respond when the expectations or outcomes of your work are unclear, and does that “ambiguity” offer potential for creative problem-solving?
5. Do you see “contradictions” as a necessary aspect of the in-between space that fuels growth and change, or as obstacles to be managed?

“Traces” of the past for the present

RK: As one of two constituent colleges of Singapore’s first arts university, our institution is caught between the binaries of vocation and profession. Having been established since 1938, we breathe in an academy that is deeply rooted with a rich legacy of educating some of the most important artistic pioneers, including 13 recipients of the Cultural Medallion—Singapore’s highest accolade for art practitioners—and 15 Young Artist Awards.

This 86-year-old academy prides itself on blending technical excellence with artistic specialisations in fine art, music, dance, theatre, design, fashion, and arts management. However, the shift towards thought leadership, contemporary artistic inquiry, and critical discourse raises the stakes in integrating tradition with innovation, urging us to reinterpret our legacy by uniting teaching, practice, and research.

As academic developers, we find ourselves uniquely positioned as intermediaries who bridge the divide between craft and scholarship, appreciating the deeply rooted influences that shape our institution’s culture: our rich heritage, the emphasis on foundational skills, and an unwavering commitment to providing transformative learning experiences across all age groups, from arts pre-school to lifelong learners at our Centre for Lifelong Learning.

EY: Yes, “traces” of our rich institutional culture has brought about an overall positive work culture of gratitude and award-winning people practices within the organisation. Our predecessors shaped environment and culture in cutting-edge recruitment practices, flexible work arrangements, grievance handling, age-friendly workplace and work-life harmony. Such initiatives steered our academy to be one of Singapore’s Best Employer for five consecutive years (from 2020 to 2024). Most recently, we were recognised at the Tripartite Alliance Award 2023: Work-Life Excellence & Leadership Award. We were also awarded the National Workplace Learning Organisation of Competence (Gold Award) in 2023, an award that has recognised us as an institution with robust and well-supported workplace learning culture that develop employees into self-driven learners, and provide them the building blocks to learn, grow and develop through continuous changes in the workplace landscape.

With a new value proposition and national agenda as the first arts university in Singapore (Chan, 2023), the firm standing of the People Excellence Office have open doors to collaboration and harmonious partnership between the administrative departments and faculty, as well as external stakeholders, such as our stable pool of industry, training partners and communities of practice. This has enabled synergies to be reaped amongst our Teaching and Learning Centre, Library, Research Division and People Excellence Office to enjoy and grow from its benefits of tapping into the respective expertise, knowledge, resources, and contacts.

“Relays” of communication and decision-making to bridge gaps

EY: With the trust that has been built over the years, the people team not only had access to core people strategic work, but also the privilege and opportunity to bridge gaps between

administration and academia. With a recent change in the national Tripartite Guidelines, we took the opportunity to align the institution's flexible work arrangement practices. As there were different practices within the institution, there were unhappiness on the ground. After listening to the needs of both administrative and academic staff, and in close consultation with Management and Union, we decided to land on the Work-From-Home policy from 2-days to 1-day per week. Due to the nature of work of the various functions within the institution, some would benefit from the revised policy, while others would not.

RK: At the Teaching and Learning Centre, we have made concerted efforts to enhance communication by actively involving administrative colleagues in academic meetings, consultations, and forums. Academic colleagues may sometimes overlook the crucial contributions of administrative staff in areas such as curriculum reviews, assessments, and the overall student learning experience. These staff members often serve as key intermediaries, managing complex interactions with adjunct lecturers and students, thus playing a pivotal role.

This collaborative approach proved particularly effective when we sought to improve participation in a new student learning experience survey. Administrative staff encountered challenges soliciting student participation due to the survey's lack of mobile accessibility, while academic colleagues expressed concerns over the potential implications of the survey results on staff evaluations.

By consulting with students, academics, and administrators, we collaboratively addressed these issues. We introduced a new survey system, developed policies to safeguard the confidentiality of results, enlisted Senior Management to encourage student participation, and implemented programmes to foster evidence-informed use of data. This not only built confidence among both academic and administrative staff but also bridged institutional divides. Ultimately, it was by demonstrating genuine care and attentiveness listening to their concerns that we were able to foster a culture of shared understanding, trust and collaboration.

“Ambivalences” as we navigate the space in-between

EY: The academy's core value of “care” has made it challenging for succession planning and talent renewal, which are essential to keep the organisation healthy, forward-looking and future ready.

But here is where I always remind myself of the purpose of my existence in the organisation. The organisational direction serves as a north star and there are key institutional priorities to achieve. Balance comes from reaching the priorities without compromising on the process and method on how it is achieved.

RK: Can you share an instance where you felt torn between conflicting professional identities or goals in this in-between space? how did you address that ambivalence?

EY: As a people strategist, I am aware that by releasing a particular employee through retirement was necessary for the team and for talent renewal within the organisation. However, the tension came as I was reminded that as a people partner, I am to uphold the organisation's core value of “care” at the same time. While I empathise with this colleague's situation, the release of this staff was an essential move towards achieving the institutional priorities in the longer run. In my capacity, I did what was necessary, and at the same time, handled the colleague, managed the situation and the exit process with dignity, respect, appreciation and care, to the best of my ability.

RK: I like to think of these tensions as a “pause” moment, what I love to call in music a “fermata”. As Fels and Belliveau (2008, p. 36) describe, these indeterminate pauses create an “provides a way to focus on the learning that emerges.” For me, learning truly takes place when there is both change and challenge. While decisions around tenure and retirement extend beyond my remit at the Teaching and Learning Centre, I find it gratifying to see colleagues depart with a wealth of transferable and transformative skill-sets, developed through the professional development workshops, dialogues and conversations that were had organised during their engagement as lecturers.

EY: Being in an established institution with a positive (and almost feels-like-family) culture, some may become complacent in their roles, especially if they do not rotate to take on other portfolios. Mindsets shifts may be a challenge and some eventually fall behind in terms of skillsets and artistic/professional practice. It is sometimes challenging to manage, but with strong support from leadership, effective change management, communication this could be managed with a good heart and in good spirit. We preach and advocate lifelong learning; where we encourage and sponsor training during office hours, provide postgraduate sponsorship to close the skills and industry gap, as much as we could. We hope to instil lifelong learning and walk-the-talk as an education institution, for our faculty and administrative colleagues alike. Our hope is that colleagues will always be hungry for knowledge and learning.

“Ambiguities” that conjure dispositions of the heart

RK: Ambiguity is the essence of artistic practice and perhaps even a defining characteristic of the arts (Kan, forthcoming). As Shulman (2012, p. 80) reminds us, “to call something ambiguous is not to claim that it is trivial or vacuous. On the contrary, it carries multiple meanings...” I think it’s important to suspend judgment, allow time for perplexity or doubt, and remain open to alternative interpretations. I like to think of such liminal pockets as what Manning and Massumi (2014) coined “enabling constraints,” which enhance creativity!

EY: Communication is key; if there is ambiguity, seek clarity. Should the expectations be open, it presents an opportunity for me to propose new ideas or approaches, and potentially explore uncharted territories as well.

RK: Yes! The musician disposition in me trains me to listen. There is both a physical and emotional aspect to listening, what Chinese call attentive listening or “ting”!

Listening with your whole heart, as being attuned to feelings, are so relevant in care-centric approaches!

I am also reminded by Gillies (2012) that the secrets of Finnish who are born young to greatness lie in their approach to the music: humility over narcissism!

EY: That makes me think of the time I had to show care and kindness in a professional setting, during a difficult conversation with a colleague. Some concerns and unhappiness were raised, and I had to facilitate the conversation and trust the process to be fair, and I had to show kindness at the same time. Space was given for this colleague to raise grievances at the meeting and thereafter, through our grievance handling avenue. At times like this, I appreciate the para-counselling course that equipped me to actively listen to others, probe deeper and facilitate challenging conversations, even if there are no answers sometimes.

RK: I completely resonate with how such dispositions can better develop our academy to be better prepared to deal with complexity and ambiguity in the today's uncertain world. As Klein (2008) reminds us, if we are to develop art teachers who are integrated, then greater attention needs to be paid to developing dispositions that reflect the inner life.

“Contradictions” as inherent conflicts that fuel growth and change

RK: It's definitely necessary to search for contradictions – these inherent tensions cultivate a deeper sensitivity to what Evans-Palmer (2017) calls “affective inclinations”.

In my work, two hearts beat as one. As a musicologist and educationalist, both identities shape my experience and approach. Embracing my role as a third space practitioner at the Teaching and Learning Centre allows me to appreciate how academic development initiatives in technology-enhanced learning, innovative pedagogies, assessment standards, and a shared core curriculum can enhance teaching and learning across all faculties.

However, as I shift to my role as a Senior lecturer in the School of Music, I recognise that there are other pressing and competing demands specific to the discipline, students, staff and the creative industry that may take precedence over educational innovations. For instance, there are nuances to be considered in how specialised and unique every discipline can be with respect to the use of technologies, how personalised pedagogies can be the individual music studio, how assessment

procedures can differ in a conservatoire-style curriculum, and how a common curriculum may not always be relevant to the drive towards hyper-specialisations in music studies.

When we engage with these contradictions, we create a space that acts as a catalyst for innovation.

EY: What does it mean in concrete terms?

RK: In practical terms, it means that I can creatively adapt and introduce pedagogies peculiar to visual arts and design to the performing arts. For instance, we've initiated creative pedagogies of transition, pedagogies of creative uncertainty, and pedagogies of designerly formation across disciplines and beyond the arts. On reflection, my third space positionality has allowed for the emergence of hybrid pedagogies, opening up new avenues for inter-disciplinarity.

EY: I actually see such tensions as a necessary aspect of growth and change. Contradictions challenge and balance academic ideals and administrative realities, as we must meet in a common ground. As the academy assumes the hood of a University, teaching staff are required to have research background and preferably a PhD. Our unique position in higher arts education would require staff to be competent in their professional artistic practice, professional knowledge in arts education, pedagogical content knowledge, and research inquiry. Unless a niche interest and trajectory, it is often challenging to find a candidate who ticks all of our boxes. Nonetheless, without the academic ideals, the needles of the administrative realities will not move and hence grow and change.

Welcoming your views

This Slowposium represents our first steps at developing a more critical reflexive dialogue to probe deep into dispositions of the heart, beyond the usual mode of sharing through conference and publication. We hope to have conveyed how the in-between space has fostered gratitude, a willingness to listen, humility, open-mindedness and the courage to create, in order to be renewed day by day. However, it will be important to consider what these dispositions look like in other contexts.

We're keen to hear from your practice, and challenges that you've been encountering.

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About the authors

Rebecca Kan

Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts, University of the Arts Singapore

ypkan@nafa.edu.sg

Associate Dean (Curriculum & Pedagogy), Teaching and Learning Centre

Associate Dean (Degree Studies), Faculty of Performing Arts

Eliza Yeo Hui

Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts, University of the Arts Singapore

Assistant Manager, People Excellence Office